

Supporting information

MS title: Unraveling genetic load dynamics during biological invasion: insights from two invasive insect species

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Appendix S1

Approximate Bayesian analyses (origin of the eastern North American population of *Harmonia axyridis*; estimation of bottleneck intensities)

1. ABC analyses: general methodology

Approximate Bayesian computation analyses (ABC; Beaumont et al. 2002) were conducted to (i) infer the invasion history of the eastern North American population of *Harmonia axyridis* and (ii) estimate the bottleneck intensities of all invasive populations for both species, *Harmonia axyridis* (two populations) and *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera* (four populations). ABC is a model-based Bayesian method that computes posterior probabilities of historical scenarios and parameter estimation using massive simulations of genetic data. All simulations and ABC analyses were performed with DIYABC-RF software (Collin et al. 2021), which integrates diyabc v1.1.54 with abcranger v1.16.69. Gene flow was not modeled in these simulations, as it is not supported by DIYABC-RF, but the software remains well-suited for Pool-Seq data and large-scale invasions.

The pool-datasets we used all consisted of 10,000 randomly selected synonymous SNPs, each of which met a minimum read count of 4 across all samples. We simulated 10,000 datasets per scenario with diyabc v1.1.54.

In all analyses, simulated and observed datasets were summarized using the complete set of summary statistics proposed by DIYABC-RF for SNP markers:

- Proportion of monomorphic loci for each population, as well as for each pair, triplet and quadruplet of populations;
- Heterozygosity for each population and for each pair of populations (mean and variance over loci; Hivert et al. 2018);
- F_{ST} -related statistics for each population (i.e., population-specific F_{ST} ; Weir and Goudet 2017), for each pair, triplet, quadruplet and overall populations when the dataset includes more than four populations (mean and variance over loci; Hivert et al. 2018);
- Allele shared Patterson's f -statistics for each triplet (f_3 -statistics) and quadruplet (f_4 -statistics) of populations (Patterson et al. 2012; mean and variance over loci; Leblois et al. 2018);
- Nei's (1972) distance for each pair of populations (mean and variance over loci);
- Maximum likelihood coefficient of admixture computed for each triplet of populations (mean and variance over loci; adapted from Choisy et al. 2004).

2. Origin of the eastern North American population of *Harmonia axyridis*

2.1 Background and motivation

The first invasive population of *Harmonia axyridis* was observed in Louisiana state in 1988 (Chapin and Brou 1991). Since then, this population has expanded across much of the eastern USA and Canada (Lombaert et al. 2014). The origin of this population was investigated using microsatellite data (Lombaert et al. 2011), and the results suggested that it originated from an admixture between the

two main genetic clusters found in the native area: the eastern cluster (China, Japan, eastern Siberia) and the western cluster (western Siberia, Kazakhstan). Recently, several unpublished pieces of evidence obtained from more numerous markers and more powerful analysis methods have suggested that this result might be incorrect, and that this invasive population might instead originate solely from the eastern native cluster. Therefore, we decided to use an ABC framework to infer the native origin of the eastern North American invasive population with the new dataset available in the present study.

2.2 ABC analyses: posterior probabilities of historical scenarios

In our competing scenarios, the eastern North American invasive population (represented by the H-I-PEN sample; see Table 1) originated from either (1) the east of the native area (represented by the H-N-CHI sample), (2) the west of the native area (represented by the H-N-RUS sample), or (3) an admixture of both.

The scenarios were coded as follows (see Figure A1 for graphical representations):

Scenario 1:

```
Ne Nw Nlou Ngh
0 sample 1
0 sample 2
0 sample 3
tlou-DBlou VarNe 3 NFlou
tlou VarNe 3 Ne
tge merge 1 3
tne merge 4 1
tnw merge 4 2
```

Scenario 2:

```
Ne Nw Nlou Ngh
0 sample 1
0 sample 2
0 sample 3
tlou-DBlou VarNe 3 NFlou
tlou VarNe 3 Nw
tgw merge 2 3
tne merge 4 1
tnw merge 4 2
```

Scenario 3:

```
Ne Nw Nlou Ngh Ne Nw
0 sample 1
0 sample 2
0 sample 3
tlou-DBlou VarNe 3 NFlou
tlou split 3 5 6 r
tge merge 1 5
tgw merge 2 6
tne merge 4 1
tnw merge 4 2
```

Population numbers are as follows: 1 for East Asia (effective population size N_e ; sample H-N-CHI); 2 for West Asia (effective population size N_w ; sample H-N-RUS); 3 for eastern North America (effective population size N_{lou} ; sample H-I-PEN); 4 for an unsampled ancestral native population (effective population size N_{gh}). The bottleneck lasts DB_{lou} generations, and the effective number of founders during this duration is NF_{lou} . The eastern North American population merges into an unsampled native population at t_{lou} . Eastern and western unsampled native populations merge into their corresponding native population at t_{ge} and t_{gw} respectively. Populations 1 and 2 merge into the ancestral native population at t_{ne} and t_{nw} , respectively. Parameter r is an admixture rate.

Historical and demographic parameter values for simulations were drawn from prior distributions defined as follows:

```
NFlou N LU[2,1000,0,0]
Ne N UN[100,100000,0,0]
Nw N UN[100,100000,0,0]
Nlou N UN[100,100000,0,0]
Ngh N LU[100,20000,0,0]
tlou T UN[68,73,0,0]
DBlou T UN[1,10,0,0]
tge T LU[68,3000,0,0]
tgw T LU[68,3000,0,0]
tne T LU[100,3000,0,0]
tnw T LU[100,3000,0,0]
r A UN[0.1,0.9,0,0]
```

With the following conditions:

```
tgw>=tlou
tge>=tlou
tnw>=tgw
tne>=tge
```


Figure A1: Schematic representation of each set of scenarios used in the ABC analyses to decipher the origin of the eastern North American population of *Harmonia axyridis*. Time is not to scale.

Since the dataset includes three populations, the total number of summary statistics was 50 (plus two LDA axes).

To compare the scenarios, we used a random forest procedure (RF; Breiman 2001; Pudlo et al. 2016). RF is a machine-learning algorithm that uses hundreds of bootstrapped decision trees to perform classification using a set of predictor variables, the summary statistics in this case. We grew a classification forest of 1000 trees based on all simulated datasets. After applying the random forest computation to the observed dataset, the scenario with the highest classification vote was selected as the most likely. Subsequently, we estimated its posterior probability using a second random forest procedure involving 1000 trees (Pudlo et al. 2016). To assess the overall performance of our ABC scenario selection, we (1) computed the prior error rate based on the available out-of-bag simulations, and (2) performed the scenario selection analysis using an alternative random selection of 10,000 synonymous SNPs, and a new reference table.

2.3 Origin of the eastern North American population of *Harmonia axyridis*: results

Our analysis suggested that scenario 1 was the most likely, indicating that the initial invasive population in North America originated from the eastern part of the Asian native area. This scenario received a total of 627 votes out of 1000, with a posterior probability of 0.764 (see table below). This conclusion was further supported by a low prior error rate (i.e. mean classification error) of 4.27%, strong robustness (Figure A2), and the analysis of the second set of SNPs which yielded 600 votes and a posterior probability of 0.720 for scenario 1 (see Table A1).

Figure A2: evaluation of the robustness of the ABC random forest analysis. Left panel: the evolution of the prior error rate (OOB error) relative to the number of trees in the forest shows that the choice of 1000 trees was sufficient. Right panel: the computation of variable importance using the Gini index showed that none of 5 noise variables added to the analysis were found among the 50 most informative statistics.

Analysis	Votes scenario 1	Votes scenario 2	Votes scenario 3	Selected scenario (post probability)
First dataset	627	18	355	1 (0.764)
Second dataset	600	41	359	1 (0.720)

Table A1: ABC random forest votes of each scenario and posterior probability of the selected scenario regarding the origin of the eastern North American population of *Harmonia axyridis*.

To conclude, the use of a large set of genetic markers, comprising 10,000 biallelic SNPs, alongside an up-to-date machine learning algorithm, yielded a distinct result compared to the findings obtained with 18 microsatellites markers by Lombaert et al. (2011). We consider the result obtained in the current study as more robust, leading us to conclude that no admixture was responsible for the invasion of *Harmonia axyridis* in eastern North America.

3. Bottleneck intensities for *Harmonia axyridis* and *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera*

3.1 Background and motivation

When a demographic bottleneck occurs in a population, it is likely to affect the genetic load. The nature of this impact theoretically depends on the intensity of the bottleneck (e.g., Glémin 2003), which results from a complex interaction between the number of founders and the duration of the bottleneck. Building on the above findings regarding the origin of the North-East American population of *Harmonia axyridis* and the abundant literature describing the invasion routes of *Harmonia axyridis* and *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera* (Miller et al. 2005; Ciosi et al. 2008; Lombaert et al. 2010, 2011, 2014, 2018), we used ABC analyses to simulate the final invasion scenarios of both species and to estimate the bottleneck intensities experienced by all invasive populations. While various parameter estimates

are already available in the literature, this approach allowed us to estimate these parameters across both species within a unified framework.

3.2 ABC analyses: simulating invasion scenario for *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera*

For *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera*, the final invasion scenario was coded as follow (see Figure A3 for a graphical representation):

```
Nm Nc Np Ncse Ninw Ngh
0 sample 1
0 sample 2
0 sample 3
0 sample 4
0 sample 5
tinw-DBinw VarNe 5 NFinw
tinw merge 3 5
tcse-DBCse VarNe 4 NFcse
tcse merge 3 4
tp-DBp VarNe 3 NFp
tp merge 2 3
tc-DBc VarNe 2 NFc
tc VarNe 2 Nm
tgm merge 1 2
tm-DBn VarNe 1 Nfm
tm merge 6 1
```

Population numbers are as follows: 1 for Mexico (effective population size N_m ; sample D-N-MX1); 2 for Colorado (effective population size N_c ; sample D-I-COL); 3 for Pennsylvania (effective population size N_p ; sample D-I-PEN); 4 for Hungary (effective population size N_{cse} ; sample D-I-HUN); 5 for North West Italy (effective population size N_{nwi} ; sample D-I-ITA); 6 for an unsampled ancestral native population (effective population size N_{gh}). All *DB* and *NF* parameters represent, respectively, the bottleneck duration and the effective number of founders during this duration for the corresponding population. All *t* parameters represent the merging time of the corresponding population with its source population. In the case of Colorado, the source is an unsampled native population that merges into the native Mexican population at time t_{gm} . The native Mexican population, in turn, merges into the ancestral population at time t_m .

Historical and demographic parameter values for simulations were drawn from prior distributions defined as follows:

```
NFinw N LU[2,1000,0,0]
Nfcse N LU[2,1000,0,0]
NFp N LU[2,1000,0,0]
Nfc N LU[2,1000,0,0]
Nm N LU[100,100000,0,0]
Nfm N LU[2,1000,0,0]
Nc N LU[100,100000,0,0]
Np N LU[100,100000,0,0]
Ncse N LU[100,100000,0,0]
Ninw N LU[100,100000,0,0]
Ngh N LU[100,100000,0,0]
tinw T UN[15,20,0,0]
DBinw T UN[1,10,0,0]
tcse T UN[23,28,0,0]
DBCse T UN[1,10,0,0]
tp T UN[30,35,0,0]
DBp T UN[1,10,0,0]
tc T LU[148,1500,0,0]
DBc T UN[1,10,0,0]
tgm T LU[148,1500,0,0]
tm T LU[148,1500,0,0]
DBn T UN[1,10,0,0]
```

With the following conditions:

$t_m > t_{gm}$
 $t_{gm} >= t_c$

Figure A3: Schematic representation of the final invasion scenario for *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera* used in the ABC analyses to estimate the bottleneck intensity of each invasive population. Time is not to scale.

Since the dataset includes five populations, the total number of summary statistics was 292.

3.3 ABC analyses: simulating invasion scenario for Harmonia axyridis

For *Harmonia axyridis* (hereafter called HA), the final invasion scenario was coded as follow (see Figure A4 for a graphical representation):

```
Ne Nw Nlou Nwas Ngh
0 sample 1
0 sample 2
0 sample 3
0 sample 4
twas-DBwas VarNe 4 NFwas
twas VarNe 4 Ne
tlou-DBlou VarNe 3 NFlou
tlou VarNe 3 Ne
tgewas merge 1 4
tgelou merge 1 3
tne merge 5 1
tnw merge 5 2
```

Population numbers are as follows: 1 for East Asia (effective population size N_e ; sample H-N-CHI); 2 for West Asia (effective population size N_w ; sample H-N-RUS); 3 for eastern North America (effective population size N_{lou} ; sample H-I-PEN); 4 for western North America (effective population size N_{was} ; sample H-I-WAS); 5 for an unsampled ancestral native population (effective population size N_{gh}). All *DB* and *NF* parameters represent, respectively, the bottleneck duration and the effective number of founders during this duration for the corresponding population. All *t* parameters represent the merging time of the corresponding population with its source population. In the case of eastern and western North American populations, the sources are unsampled native populations that merge into the native east Asian population at the corresponding time t_{ge} . The native populations, in turn, merge into the ancestral population at the corresponding time t_n .

Historical and demographic parameter values for simulations were drawn from prior distributions defined as follows:

```

Ngh N LU[100,20000,0,0]
NFwas N LU[2,1000,0,0]
Ne N UN[100,100000,0,0]
NFlou N LU[2,1000,0,0]
Nw N UN[100,100000,0,0]
Nlou N UN[100,100000,0,0]
Nwas N UN[100,100000,0,0]
twas T UN[60,65,0,0]
DBwas T UN[1,10,0,0]
tlou T UN[68,73,0,0]
DBlou T UN[1,10,0,0]
tgewas T LU[60,3000,0,0]
tgelou T LU[68,3000,0,0]
tne T LU[100,3000,0,0]
tnw T LU[100,3000,0,0]

```

With the following conditions:

```

tgelou>=tlou
tne>=tgelou
tgewas>=twas
tne>=tgewas

```


Figure A4: Schematic representation of the final invasion scenario for *Harmonia axyridis* used in the ABC analyses to estimate the bottleneck intensity of each invasive population. Thin lines indicate a bottleneck. Time is not to scale.

Since the dataset includes four populations, the total number of summary statistics was 130.

3.4 ABC analyses: estimating bottleneck intensities

For each scenario, we first assessed their goodness-of-fit by determining whether priors were off target, comparing the distributions of simulated summary statistics with the value of the observed dataset. Then, for each invasive population of both species, we estimated the composite parameter *DB/NF* using a regression by random forest methodology (Raynal et al. 2019), with classification forests consisting of 1,000 trees. This composite parameter allows us to measure the relative intensity of the bottleneck by incorporating both the effect of demography (*NF*, effective number of founder) and time (*DB*, bottleneck duration), which are intrinsically linked and whose effects on genetic diversity are difficult to disentangle.

3.5 Estimation of bottleneck intensities: results

Comparisons of the distributions of simulated summary statistics with values from the observed dataset showed that the combination of scenarios and priors we chose was realistic. Indeed, only 17 out of 292 observed statistics (5.8%) for *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera* and 4 out of 130 observed statistics (3.1%) for *Harmonia axyridis* significantly (at a 5% threshold) lay in the tails of the probability distribution of statistics calculated from prior simulations.

Point estimates of composite parameter DB/NF (hereafter referred to as “bottleneck intensity”) for all invasive populations of both species are presented in Figure A5. Overall, bottlenecks were found to be less severe in *Harmonia axyridis* (HA) than in *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera* (DVV). In DVV, only the Pennsylvania population (D-I-PEN) suffered a modest bottleneck, similar to those observed in the HA populations, which may be explained by its spatial connection to its source population in Colorado (Lombaert et al. 2018). The two European DVV populations show similar, relatively high bottleneck intensities. Finally, the oldest invasive DVV population in Colorado (D-I-COL) shows high estimates of bottleneck intensity, but with very large ranges, so these results should be interpreted with caution.

Figure A5: Estimation of the composite parameter DB/NF (bottleneck duration / effective number of founder) for each invasive population of *Harmonia axyridis* and *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera*. For each population, point estimates are the mean (blue triangle), the median (red circle), the 0.05 quantile (lower dash line) and the 0.95 quantile (upper dash line).

Appendix S2

Computation of the R_{XY} statistic

The R_{XY} statistic measures the relative excess or deficit of a specific category of variant (either missense or loss-of-function) in an invasive population (population X) compared to its source population (population Y). It is computed as described by Xue et al. (2015). For each category of non-synonymous mutation, we first calculate the following two ratios:

$$L_{X,Y}(C) = \frac{\sum_{i \in C} p_i^X q_i^Y}{\sum_{j \in S} p_j^X q_j^Y}$$

and:

$$L_{Y,X}(C) = \frac{\sum_{i \in C} p_i^Y q_i^X}{\sum_{j \in S} p_j^Y q_j^X}$$

Where p represents derived allele frequencies, q represents ancestral allele frequencies, i and j are nucleotide sites, C is the set of a specific category of non-synonymous protein-coding sites (either missense or loss-of-function), and S is the set of synonymous sites.

The ratio statistic is then defined as:

$$R_{X/Y}(C) = \frac{L_{X,Y}(C)}{L_{Y,X}(C)}$$

Figure S1: Known invasion routes of (a) *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera* and (b) *Harmonia axyridis*. Native areas are shown in green and invasive areas in red. The dashed line in the native range of *Harmonia axyridis* roughly delineates the western and eastern genetic clusters. Green arrows indicate introductions from a native population, while red arrows indicate introductions from an already invasive population. Years of first observation for invasive populations are indicated. Invasion routes were reconstructed from several previous studies (Miller et al. 2005; Ciosi et al. 2008; Lombaert et al. 2010, 2011, 2018), as well as the present study (see Appendix S1).

Figure S2: Distribution of est-sfs probabilities for each species and target population. The vertical dashed red lines illustrate the threshold applied in this study.

Figure S3: Number of polarized SNPs as a function of the est-sfs probability threshold.

(a)

(b)

Figure S4: Pairwise F_{ST} estimates between all sample pairs of (a) *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera* and (b) *Harmonia axyridis*. The error bars represent the 95% confidence interval computed from standard errors obtained through 100-block Jackknife resampling.

Population code name	Species name	BioSample accession	SRA accession
D-N-MX1	<i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>	SAMN40074446	SRR28065669; SRR28065666; SRR28065667
D-N-MX2	<i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>	SAMN40074447	SRR28065665; SRR28065663; SRR28065664
D-I-COL	<i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>	SAMN40074444	SRR28065674; SRR28065675; SRR28065673
D-I-PEN	<i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>	SAMN40074445	SRR28065671; SRR28065672; SRR28065670
D-I-HUN	<i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>	SAMN40074443	SRR28065677; SRR28065678; SRR28065676
D-I-ITA	<i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>	SAMN40074442	SRR28065652; SRR28065653; SRR28065654
H-N-CHI	<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>	SAMN40074435	SRR28065680
H-N-RUS	<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>	SAMN40074436	SRR28065679
H-I-PEN	<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>	SAMN40074437	SRR28065668
H-I-WAS	<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>	SAMN40074438	SRR28065658
D-OG-ADE	<i>Diabrotica adelpha</i>	SAMN40074448	SRR28065662
D-OG-TRI	<i>Cerotoma trifurcata</i>	SAMN40074451	SRR28065659
H-OG-YED	<i>Harmonia yedoensis</i>	SAMN40074439	SRR28065657
H-OG-CON	<i>Harmonia conformis</i>	SAMN40074440	SRR28065656
H-OG-QUA	<i>Harmonia quadripunctata</i>	SAMN40074441	SRR28065655

Table S1: Biosample and Sequence Read Archive (SRA) accessions for all samples used in this study (see Table 1 for additional information). All references can be found in public databases within BioProject PRJNA1079689: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA1079689>

Sample	Capture 1	Capture 2	Capture 3	Capture 4	Capture 5
D-N-MX1	250	0	250	250	0
D-N-MX2	0	250	250	0	250
D-I-COL	250	0	250	250	0
D-I-PEN	0	250	250	0	250
D-I-HUN	250	250	0	0	250
D-I-ITA	250	250	0	250	0
D-OG-ADE	0	0	0	83.4	0
D-OG-TRI	0	0	0	83.4	0

Table S2: Quantity of amplified DNA (in nanograms) per population and outgroup samples within each *Diabrotica virgifera virgifera* exome capture reaction. See Table 1 for correspondence of sample names.

Sample	Capture 1	Capture 2
H-N-CHI	475	0
H-N-RUS	0	475
H-I-PEN	475	0
H-I-WAS	0	475
H-OG-YED	0	25
H-OG-CON	25	0
H-OG-QUA	25	0

Table S3: Quantity of amplified DNA (in nanograms) per population and outgroup samples within each *Harmonia axyridis* exome capture reaction. See Table 1 for correspondence of sample names.

Species	Population code name	Total number of read pairs	Mbases	Number of cleaned read pairs	Number of cleaned reads (SE1 only)	Number of cleaned reads (SE2 only)	Total number of cleaned reads	Proportion of reads retained (%)
<i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>	D-N-MX1	44,817,432	13445.23	23,853,708	12,983,827	1,207,657	38,045,192	84.9%
<i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>	D-N-MX2	49,240,579	14772.17	27,135,813	13,481,989	1,498,006	42,115,808	85.5%
<i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>	D-I-COL	46,195,866	13858.76	24,560,305	13,431,214	1,298,675	39,290,194	85.1%
<i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>	D-I-PEN	44,388,533	13316.56	24,128,204	12,475,387	1,246,443	37,850,034	85.3%
<i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>	D-I-HUN	60,055,627	18016.69	34,093,035	15,300,849	1,879,292	51,273,176	85.4%
<i>Diabrotica virgifera virgifera</i>	D-I-ITA	56,482,967	16944.89	31,582,786	13,682,870	2,100,689	47,366,345	83.9%
<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>	H-N-CHI	71,236,915	21371.07	48,980,633	16,721,947	1,528,100	67,230,680	94.4%
<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>	H-N-RUS	62,668,899	18800.67	43,204,013	15,016,778	1,368,480	59,589,271	95.1%
<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>	H-I-PEN	60,105,748	18031.72	39,582,696	8,821,330	6,341,663	54,745,689	91.1%
<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>	H-I-WAS	59,431,143	17829.34	40,720,319	14,150,309	1,308,966	56,179,594	94.5%
<i>Diabrotica adelpha</i>	D-OG-ADE	5,357,457	1607.24	3,921,123	1,254,138	33,513	5,208,774	97.2%
<i>Diabrotica balteata</i>	D-OG-BAL	3,839,170	1151.75	2,887,561	818,348	27,020	3,732,929	97.2%
<i>Diabrotica undecimpunctata howardi</i>	D-OG-UND	3,569,247	1070.77	2,857,981	597,593	43,982	3,499,556	98.0%
<i>Cerotoma trifurcata</i>	D-OG-TRI	735,945	220.78	581,422	123,845	10,341	715,608	97.2%
<i>Harmonia yedoensis</i>	H-OG-YED	2,008,136	602.44	1,576,084	392,346	14,198	1,982,628	98.7%
<i>Harmonia conformis</i>	H-OG-CON	1,810,155	543.05	1,540,507	233,331	16,630	1,790,468	98.9%
<i>Harmonia quadripunctata</i>	H-OG-QUA	1,102,318	330.69	961,755	121,459	9,229	1,092,443	99.1%

Table S4: Summary statistics for the raw sequence data obtained for the 17 libraries (10 focal species and 7 outgroup species). SE1 and SE2 denote the first and second ends of paired-end reads, respectively. See Table S1 for BioSample and SRA accessions.

Species	Raw vcf size after calling	Bi-allelic SNPs only	Filtered bi-allelic SNPs (polarized)	Coding regions only (polarized)	Synonymous (polarized)	Non synonymous (NS)	
						NS missense (polarized)	NS LoF (polarized)
<i>Diabrotica v. virgifera</i>	3,795,499	2,789,733	263,639 (254,309)	66,274 (62,212)	37,559 (34,164)	27,808 (27,146)	907 (902)
<i>Harmonia axyridis</i>	4,044,301	2,647,316	411,679 (410,595)	169,755 (169,223)	116,190 (115,740)	52,307 (52,226)	1,258 (1,257)

Table S5: Total number of SNPs called and retained at each stage of the pipeline for each species. Where applicable, the number of positions successfully polarized is shown in brackets. The last three columns correspond to SNPs from coding regions categorized by SNPEFF: synonymous, missense and loss-of-function (LoF) mutations.

Supporting information references

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